

APPLICATIONS AND CHALLENGES OF PREPREG FORMING TECHNOLOGIES IN AIRCRAFT INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

For manufacturing of lightweight aircraft structures, stiffened panels are a main element. In the industrial manufacturing process the prepreg forming process is closing the gap between the efficient production of laminates with automated processes and the requirement of complex profile production. However, a high quality result from the forming process is not trivial to achieve and changing materials and shapes for new implementations are creating a constant challenge for process development. Recently, some progress has been made in the field of process simulation but still deeper understanding on the material behaviour is required to further increase the efficiency of the forming processes and successfully compete with different composite manufacturing strategies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural aircraft components typically consist of thin skin fields which are reinforced with stiffener elements – stringers – in longitudinal direction. In perpendicular direction, those panels are reinforced with frames in case of a fuselage component or with ribs and spars in case of box structures (e.g. wings or tail planes) to create a closed shear profile and form a structural assembly.

Efficient manufacturing technologies are necessary to produce those reinforcing elements - like stringers or spars - in order to offer a competitive product. Nowadays, carbon fiber composite (CFRP) material is selected very often due to the high mechanical performance of the material. In such a case, pre-impregnated (prepreg) semi-finished material is preferred compared to textiles for elements of the primary structure and automated lay-up processes –such as Automated Tape Laying (ATL) or Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) technologies – can be applied to deliver the output demanded. However, state of the art technologies are currently able to exploit their full potential mainly during the generation of flat or only slightly curved large sized laminates; the more complex the structure the more difficult and slow the lay-up process [8].

Therefore, forming processes are applied to create three dimensional structural components from those flat laminates like e. g C shaped spars. Usually, a laminate is heated up to a defined temperature and a specific mechanism applies a force onto the laminate – e.g. utilizing an elastomeric membrane, or directly via a moving hard tooling - until the desired shape is realized.

Airbus produces a large variety of composite elements/parts in-house whereas the length of the formed profiles differs from less than one meter up to more than 30m with a laminate thickness between 0.8mm up to 20mm depending on the specific product. Additionally to the manifold geometry different production rates and lead time has to be considered depending on the specific program. For such big portfolio it is unlikely that one single process is the optimum choice for all profiles. For that reason several processes - adapted to the specific parts - are in place, whereas dedicated ones will be discussed in the following. Considering the complete aircraft even thicker laminates are formed e.g. in the keel beam area which requires special process modifications.

2 GENERAL PRODUCTION PROCESS

In this section, an overview will be given on the main geometries and the overall production processes as well as applied forming processes.

2.1 PROFILE GEOMETRY

The main field of application for prepreg forming processes can be found in the production of stiffening elements. Spars and stringers are required in large quantities for aircraft panels. To give some more detailed examples: on each of the four A350 XWB wing covers almost 300m of stringers are placed which sum up to about 1.2 km of stringers in total per aircraft, or, all skin panels of the outer and middle flaps for one A380 aircraft are equipped with approximately one kilometer of stringers, too.

Figure 1: Profile production sequence for cured T-stringer (1. Forming; 2. Joining and curing; 3. Trimming; 4. Final profiles)

In composite part production the most relevant profile geometry is a T shape cross section. The Ω (also called hat) shape is often implemented as well, whereas I (or double T) profiles are used not so often usually due to economic reasons in production.

Focusing on the T-stringer type, there are several different ways of production which are mainly depending on the integration and curing strategy (Co-bonding, Co-curing or secondary bonding).

In case of the integration of cured stringers, those are separately cured and usually also machined before joining with the skin part. One effective manufacturing approach is to create one H-Profile from two C-shaped parts and to separate those on the web section after curing by cutting (see fig. 1).

In case of an integration of the wet profiles into the skin part, the above mentioned strategy is not feasible because the final shape is only available after machining of the cured component.

Alternatively, either a complete cover layer can be made up from U-Profiles, which are joined side by side after forming, or single L-profiles can be produced to form the T-shape and then be placed individually on the skin part.

The production of U (or C) shaped parts has the advantage of easier positioning and fixation on mandrels and results in two formed webs in one handling step compared to the L-shape.

Spars are usually C- Shaped (or flat, in which case no forming is required) and can be formed like U-shaped stringers. In highly loaded parts, like e. g. wing cover or tail planes structures, spars may have a significantly increased laminate thickness compared to usual stringers.

2.2 FORMING PROCESSES

The most common forming process is the well-known diaphragm - or hot drape - forming. A heated laminate is formed using a rigid mandrel resembling the inner geometry of the desired part by a membrane –or diaphragm- placed above the laminate.

Figure 2: Schematic of a double diaphragm forming process

The required force is applied to the laminate through the evacuation of air from the sealed space below the diaphragm which is illustrated in fig. 2. Due to the elasticity of the diaphragm material it is adapting to the mandrel geometry forcing the laminate into position.

The basic principle of the process is easily described and relatively simple to implement in the form of a basic drape forming machine. The challenge is to control numerous parameters in the machine set-up and forming operation including temperature, time, power of the heating devices, material properties and tension of the diaphragm material, movement of the frame, applied vacuum etc.

The above listed parameters control the process, but are acting only indirectly on the properties and internal condition of the laminate, which is determining the final result of the forming operation; e. g. the material properties of the laminate - mainly determined by the temperature which may vary in different locations of the part -, the movement rate between adjacent plies, the deformation of the individual plies, the elongation transferred from the stretched membrane, etc.

As those relevant process factors can only be manipulated indirectly throughout the forming operation, process control remains a challenge for this process. The main benefit is the flexibility due to the use of different mandrels / forming tools in one machine with a “universal” membrane.

An alternative process is to include a second diaphragm below the material and use a defined level of vacuum in between both membranes to increase guiding of the material. On the one side, this double diaphragm approach ensures a better heat exchange and allows forming of shapes with an increased level of complexity. On the other side, additional parameters need to be controlled resulting in an increased complexity of the machine and the process.

In cases of high volume production, a reduction in variability of the forming process makes sense. Processes are available which implement a forming procedure based on mechanically induced movements and rigid forming tools resulting in a less flexible application due to those tools. In comparison to automated processes for mass production manual lay up of parts is still an appropriate process for small sized or limited series production for the following reasons:

- Increasing complexity and decreasing size reduce efficiency of well-established automated processes, as the huge machines are not able to reach their maximum potential like e. g. movement speed over short distances. Small robot based AFP machines could fill this gap, but currently deposition rates for complex geometries are still relatively low.
→ In this case, manual lay-up of single plies results in a good and consistent layup quality especially for convex shapes, but of course depends heavily on operator skills.
- Set up cost for small series parts are exceeding possible productivity benefits of automated processes, which is true for NC programming and nesting of layup and cutting as well as process setup for forming.

3 CHALLENGES

Although prepreg forming is applied for more than 20 years in aircraft industry several challenges have to be faced whereas main topics will be illustrated in the following.

3.1 NEW PARTS

In general, the implementation of a new part into serial production requires a huge testing effort because knowledge from other/ previous parts can only be used partially. Changes in one or more of the following parameters may lead to significantly different forming results:

- Change of the material of the laminate
- Modification of geometric features (ramp geometry, shape)
- Thickness, size changes
- Quality requirements (e.g. geometric tolerances resulting from the requirements of subsequent assembly steps)

Anyway, economic considerations have to be taken into account for any new part e.g. fiber placement processes which are able to lay up more complex geometry directly may result in omitting forming processes for specific cases. In general, transfer of knowledge should be done very carefully, because slight differences like e. g. toughening agents may lead to unexpected results.

The variety of existing – and for aircraft primary structural applications qualified – prepreg systems, is an advantage for the fine tuning of cost and performance compared to textile applications.

3.2 INCREASE OF PRODUCTIVITY

The industrial goal is to produce highest quality parts with reduced cost and to optimize the performance of the product (e.g. weight saving) which increases in some cases the geometrical complexity and requires sophisticated fine tuning of all parameters.

One possible driver for productivity increase of the process is heat control, as heat up and cool down cycles dominate the process time. E. g. dwell stages are usually applied to get a homogeneous temperature distribution in the part, better control and adaptability of the heating cycles and an effective, reliable temperature measurement on the laminate to start forming as soon as the required conditions are met.

3.3 PROCESS SIMULATION

Process optimization based on experimental testing usually requires full scale tests. Given the high cost of the components compared to the relatively low number of parts to be produced (e.g. in comparison to consumer goods or automotive application) often results in an insufficient business case. This limits the full exploitation of the potential of these forming processes. This imbalance is getting even worse if not only process parameters are to be optimized, but also the effect of hardware modifications is to be investigated.

A more economical alternative to the cost intensive experimental optimization process can be found in the availability of reliable simulation models for material behavior during the forming process.

Different models to simulate and predict forming behavior are available since a certain time whereas they have been developed in the light of fabric materials or manual fiber draping. One well-established theory is the so called pin jointed net (PJN) method. This theory assumes a known and fixed net of joints inside the material (e.g. the cross links in fabric material). In general, this approach can be applied to prepreg tape materials, too, assuming the unknown net size. This theory is capable to describe the variation of fiber angles due to the forming as long as the material behavior is not deviating too far from the initial assumptions. However, for modern generation prepreg systems this cannot be assumed easily as demonstrated by recent results [2].

For prepreg material especially tape material, theories based only on kinematic behavior are not sufficient anymore. The final condition is not determined by the initial condition and the geometry alone, it also depends on the varying friction between the plies, the deformability of the material and the transfer of loads within the material. To give a rough order of magnitude: Under standard forming conditions of each material, the difference in interply friction from two different generations of prepreg material currently in use is one to two magnitudes higher for a current generation material than for previous materials [6]. It is clear that under such preconditions material behavior has to be taken into account if a simulation approach shall deliver meaningful results.

Recently, some progress has been made in the field of numerical simulation of the forming process [3, 9] implemented in FE analysis. Different parameters to describe interply friction and viscoelastic in-plane deformation behavior are required which are usually not determined during today's material characterization. Additionally, those parameters show a dependency on the processing temperature and other parameters which cannot be assumed to be linear. Material models to reflect the parameter variation need further refinement and validation.

Furthermore, some effects seen in real world applications cannot be covered by this approach. At a certain level of temperature and pressure on the material resin flow is becoming important. This has two implications: at first the dominant material properties change from viscoelastic to the viscous domain – with e.g. permeability and local pressure gradients becoming more relevant – and, therefore, different calculation methods are required. The second implication is that the local material composition is changes, further altering of the material properties on a local scale can be found.

However, first successful steps have been demonstrated and commercial solutions exist to allow forming simulation under the given assumptions showing first promising results.

For a wider application of this method some prerequisites have to be fulfilled:

- Further validation of the results of the forming simulation have to be performed to prove the limits of applicability for varying conditions
- The implementation in a standard FEA software is preferred, at least as a basic and verifiable reference even if final full scale process simulation can require a more optimized and tailored solution
- Improvements need to be made in the material models to allow for an efficient material characterization also taking into account external parameter dependencies (temperature, pressure, etc.)

From the current point of view especially the material model is the most critical point. In [2] it is indicated, that friction for different generations of prepreg material is not following the same basic

models, presumably due to the amount and type of toughening agents used in the material. It is elaborated that basic material models from geology may be suited to describe the friction behavior of the material, whereas adaptations are needed.

To characterize a material - especially with a strong non-linear temperature (as our primary parameter, but also for the viscosity, as the dependent parameter) dependency - a high number of tests are required for all relevant process parameters. This is not only relevant for the friction behavior, but also for the in plane viscoelastic properties. A clear view for relevant and non-relevant parameters cannot be given at this point.

Not only properties of the prepreg material itself are relevant for the result of a forming process. Often a sequence of auxiliary materials is placed on the laminate stack to serve different functions. It is known from practical experience that the properties of those materials and the interactions between each adjacent material and the membrane on the top of the stack as well as the forming tool are relevant for the result of the forming process, too. This is further increases the testing effort to fully cover all relevant material properties.

Commercially available solutions implement specific shell elements to reduce complexity and calculation time. However, for calibration and verification of the material models – as well as the applied shell solution - an implementation with volume elements still seems beneficial, even if a full scale forming processes will not be possible to be solved due to the massive required processing power - under the assumption that an economical benefit needs to be achieved with limited resource assignment.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Progress on the theoretical understanding of prepreg forming processes leads to extended opportunities in the industrial applicability and, thus, a further exploitation of the potential. This paper is meant to provide a better view on the possible applications in general and requirements in the development phase for an increased number of applications; especially in the light of a demanding competition between different composite manufacturing processes.

A very important step to increase process efficiency and the reduction of development efforts – both for optimization of existing parts and the implementation of new applications – can be found in the field of numerical simulation, which is feeding the basic knowledge on the process principles, especially in the field of material behavior.

Fortunately, research in forming processes has been progressed recently and is delivers promising results to be used in industrial applications. Still there are many questions open especially on the material models. In the long term, it is required to refine existing models and define a comprehensive set of tests to fully characterize the formability of a certain material. In best case conditions, material manufacturers will deploy those tests and also use the results to optimize formability of their materials, especially considering upcoming alternative processes for non prepreg primary structures.

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